

TRUST WITHOUT CERTIFICATION: A USER-CENTERED APPROACH TO TRUSTWORTHINESS

Lauren Work

Yale University Library
USA
lauren.work@yale.edu
0000-0002-0941-6921

Shira Peltzman

Yale University Library
USA
shira.peltzman@yale.edu
0000-0003-0067-2782

Abstract – This paper examines the evolving concept of trust in digital preservation, considering how repositories can cultivate trust outside the bounds of formal certification. Drawing on Yale University Library’s 2024 certification readiness assessment and the trust model proposed by Yakel *et al.*, we explore how three key factors they identify—integrity, identification, and structural assurance—are reflected in Yale’s preservation activities and practices. We demonstrate how user-centered strategies such as transparent operations, consistent service delivery, and sustained stakeholder engagement can function as effective mechanisms for establishing trust, even in the absence of external assessment. This reframing signals an important stage of maturity within the field and invites the digital preservation community to reconsider how trust is conceptualized, built, and evaluated.

Submission Type – Full Paper.

Keywords – Repository Assessment, Audit Certification, Trust.

Conference Topics – Journey, (Haerenga).

I. INTRODUCTION

As digital preservation programs mature, many face the question of whether and how to pursue formal certification as a Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR). Certification standards like ISO 16363 [1] offer structured criteria for assessing internal policies, technical infrastructure, and organizational accountability. Yet for many institutions, the process can be resource-intensive and difficult to align with local priorities, especially when the primary aim is to build and sustain trust with users.

At Yale University Library, we have revisited the question of certification multiple times. Over the last decade, we have developed a steadily maturing digital preservation program, supported by significant institutional investment, cross-unit collaboration, and a robust technical infrastructure. Throughout this time there have been several opportunities to pursue formal certification. In 2024, following a leadership transition and organizational restructuring, we revisited the question once again vis-à-vis a certification readiness assessment to reevaluate the value and feasibility of certification. Ultimately we again decided not to pursue certification, which raised important questions about the nature of user trust.

This prompted important internal conversations about the nature of trust in digital preservation: what does it mean for a repository to be trusted, and how can that trust be demonstrated, earned, or maintained? Is certification the most effective way to demonstrate trustworthiness for our users? To explore these questions, we turned to the work of Yakel *et al.* [2], whose empirical study on data reusers’ trust in data repositories tested a five-factor model of trust: integrity, identification, structural assurance, benevolence, and transparency. Of these, three factors—integrity, identification, and structural assurance—were found to be most positively correlated with trust among repository users. Unlike traditional frameworks that often center policy and

internal procedures, Yakel *et al.*'s model offers a user-focused lens on trust that provides an alternative set of possibilities for trust-building.

In this paper we explore how Yale's digital preservation activities align with and contribute to this emergent model. Drawing on insights from an internal certification readiness assessment, and current and ongoing work, we demonstrate how trust is enacted according to each of the three positively correlated factors Yakel *et al.* identify, and consider how these activities can serve to further articulate nascent models to strengthen user trust as well as provide additional pathways to formal certification. In doing so, we contribute to a broader conversation within the digital preservation community about how user trust can be meaningfully assessed, communicated, and operationalized even in the absence of formal certification. This shift toward a more user-centered understanding of trust both signals a maturation of the digital preservation field itself, and advances a more nuanced discourse on trust that reconsiders how repositories can demonstrate trustworthiness in practice.

II. DIGITAL PRESERVATION AT YALE

With a campus-wide mandate to ensure the long-term preservation of Yale's digital collections, the digital preservation team at Yale University Library is responsible for preserving a wide range of digital content to ensure its future accessibility and usability [3]. This includes material digitized through library projects, born-digital assets from both special and general collections, and digital content contributed by 19 units across the campus community, including Yale's museums and galleries.

Yale's formal engagement with digital preservation began in the early 2000s with the implementation of the Rescue Repository, a rudimentary file-level system designed to reduce the risk of data loss [4]. Though basic, the system remained in use for more than a decade, well beyond its intended lifespan. A significant turning point came in 2013 with the appointment of Yale's first Digital Preservation

Manager, Euan Cochrane, ushering in a more strategic and sustained commitment to digital stewardship. Following a period of requirements gathering, cost modeling, and advocacy, we selected Preservica as our enterprise repository solution. Collection ingest began in earnest in 2016, and since then, we have ingested over 133 million files—an average of 1.4 million files per month—totaling more than 1.25 petabytes of data.

Over the years, the program has grown steadily in its staffing level, technical maturity, infrastructural complexity, and the visibility and impact of its work across the institution. A particularly decisive shift came when Yale established a policy requiring that digital content be ingested into Preservica as a prerequisite for exposure in key access platforms, including Yale's Digital Collections System (DCS) and our Aviary repository for audiovisual material. By making preservation a dependency for access, digital preservation moved from a background service to a visible, indispensable layer of Yale's digital ecosystem. This mandate fundamentally raised the profile of the program, embedding preservation as a non-negotiable step in the content lifecycle and positioning the team as essential to the institution's ability to provide discovery and use.

Today, digital preservation at Yale is marked by a high degree of institutional commitment and is supported by five full-time staff: three Digital Preservation Librarians, a Born Digital Specialist, and the Head of Digital Preservation. Yale now operates four instances of Preservica—among the largest deployments globally. Integrations with systems such as ArchivesSpace and multiple custom-built workflow management tools facilitate automated metadata generation and content exchange. Strong, ongoing partnerships with Central and Library IT, along with active collaboration with Yale's Development and Operations and Software Engineering teams, and a service contract with Preservica, enable the program to support our users through bespoke workflows, custom-built applications, and extensive API integrations.

III. PAST CERTIFICATION EFFORTS

As the program grew in visibility and maturity, questions emerged about how best to demonstrate our trustworthiness. This led to a series of exploratory work towards TDR certification—none of which ultimately advanced to the formal certification stage. In 2016, when collection ingest into the preservation repository was nascent, two staff members completed training with the Primary Trustworthy Digital Repository Authorisation Body (PTAB), an accredited body that can conduct training and serve as auditors for ISO 16363, in preparation for certification. This initiative did not move forward, which was due in part to competing priorities and limited resources. During the program's early years, our highest priorities were to address the significant backlogs of at-risk content that had accreted, and to build systems and services that functioned well for our users. We accomplished this by lowering barriers to participation wherever possible by accepting submission of content into the repository in whatever form partners could provide, avoiding prescriptive requirements, and shifting the burden of technical processing and packaging work away from our users. Our efforts with units were high-touch and resource intensive, but this approach was critical to building trust and fostering engagement. Although certification was desirable, our capacity was too limited. Instead, in 2017, we elected to pursue a lighter-weight repository self-assessment using the first version of the NDSA Levels of Preservation as a framework to identify areas for improvement [5].

By 2019, after two additional Digital Preservation Librarians had come onboard, the digital preservation team again underwent PTAB training alongside several members of Library IT. By this point in time, the repository had become highly integrated with other library systems, which significantly increased the complexity of the certification process. Certification once again fell by the wayside. Instead, we pursued a systematic review and gap analysis of current Yale practice

against the metrics outlined in ISO 16363, led by Digital Preservation Librarian Grete Graf. This was then supplemented in following years with self-assessments using the Digital Preservation Coalition's (DPC) Rapid Assessment Model (RAM), which has been used annually since 2022 [6].

IV. 2024 CERTIFICATION READINESS ASSESSMENT

While earlier certification attempts stalled due to resource limitations and competing priorities, recent leadership and organizational transitions provided a renewed opportunity to reflect systematically on whether external certification aligned with our evolving goals. In 2024, we undertook a self-designed certification readiness assessment, led by Digital Preservation Librarian Lauren Work, to gain a further understanding of the current perspectives on assessment and certification. The scope of the initial readiness assessment was purposefully limited to the digital preservation unit and therefore did not incorporate perspectives of key library partners. All members of the digital preservation team were asked to reflect on several questions that were adapted from an assessment framework from the DPC Handbook Audit and Certification chapter [7]. Written answers to each question were collated then used to create a snapshot dataset and a corresponding analysis of our current views on intrinsic and extrinsic benefits/incentives of certification,[8] and to identify further themes and questions related to the digital preservation program pursuing an external certification. We held a group discussion reflecting on and affirming the findings of this assessment.

One theme that emerged repeatedly throughout our certification readiness assessment was the potential for the pursuit of certification to act as both an enhancement or a hindrance. Staff clearly recognized the expected benefits to the repository's reputation that certification would bring, but this was tempered with concerns about resource intensity of the certification process and, critically, the capacity it would require. Staff expressed doubts about how the multi-year process and resources needed for an

external certification would impact existing digital preservation services and infrastructural needs, and posited that trust could potentially be more effectively built with stakeholders through other methods *not* limited to external certification.

The results of the certification readiness assessment surfaced previously unarticulated skepticism about the value of attaining formal certification as a trustworthy repository. The questions raised during this discussion related to trust merited further consideration of digital preservation community research on how trust relationships with stakeholders have been previously discussed and studied.

V. LITERATURE REVIEW AND RELATED WORK

The issues raised during the certification readiness assessment underscored that our questions were not unique to Yale, but part of a broader discourse within the digital preservation community that recent scholarship has increasingly begun to address. Much of the existing digital preservation literature related to audit and certification covers the guidelines and standards themselves, publicly available documentation produced by certified repositories as part of the certification requirements, and institutional use case reports [8]. More recently, however, research has expanded to include critiques and evaluations of the frameworks for trustworthy digital repository assessment themselves [9], [10], [11], [12], and the complexity of trust and how it operates between repositories and their designated communities and stakeholders. In this paper we focus on the latter area, as it aligns with questions around trust that emerged during our certification readiness assessment.

Standards for trustworthy digital repositories such as ISO 16363, aim to provide an objective measurement of trustworthiness through structured criteria [1], [13], [14]. Yet, the ways in which stakeholders and designated communities actually perceive and associate trust with certification remains an evolving area of inquiry. This emerging body of research

reflects the growing recognition that trust extends beyond technical compliance. It points toward more user-centered conceptions of trust that encompass relational and contextual dimensions in addition to technical and procedural assurances. Related work includes studies that compare specific factors that may affect trust for two specific designated communities [15] and examine users' perspectives on trust in digital repositories [16], articulate how user perceptions of trust may improve trust in TDR standards [17] and calls for increased study and understanding of how designated communities engage with and use data preserved by repositories [18], [19]. Of this relatively small subset of research focused on factors that may influence repository users' trust of repositories, we found the recent empirical study conducted by Yakel *et al.* to be a useful proposed model through which we can begin to examine the themes related to trust we identified during our certification readiness assessment.

The study examines factors that influence data users' trust in a specific data repository, as well as factors that influence trust on their intention to continue using it. Based on a quantitative study design, their analysis found three trustworthiness factors that are positively related to data reuser trust in repositories; integrity, identification, and structural assurance.

Integrity is defined by the study as consistency of actions; of setting and meeting expectations and service levels. Integrity is adherence to principles—that the data are valid, and that the data repository is not misleading users.

Identification is related to the importance of understanding and responding to the changing needs of designated communities, and the ability to receive input from users and understand the disciplinary practice of communities.

Structural assurance includes organizational level factors, regulations or safeguards, reputation, and third party endorsements. It may also encompass positive results from assessments for digital repositories, including through certification systems for trustworthy digital repositories.

While Yakel *et al.*'s study focuses on a single repository and a narrowly defined user group, the proposed model offers a valuable lens for evaluating trust from a user-centric perspective. Notably, it shifts the emphasis away from internal repository functions toward observable actions that foster trust externally, and invites repositories to consider how they actively demonstrate integrity, responsiveness, and structural reliability to their user communities.

VI. IMPLICATIONS OF THIS MODEL FOR YALE

Building on this body of work, we next examine how the trust model proposed by Yakel *et al.* can be considered within the Yale context, viewing the findings of our own assessment and resource allocations through the lens of a user-centered conception of trust. By illustrating that trust is multifaceted and that formal certification is only one element within a broader ecosystem of trust, Yakel *et al.*'s study provides a valuable model for considering the ways that trust in a digital preservation repository may be assessed and built. It affirms the view articulated during our certification readiness assessment that trust can potentially be effectively fostered through alternative, and potentially more impactful, strategies.

The Yakel *et al.* findings lend empirical support to this approach and provide a unique opportunity to consider how a user-centered approach to trust-building may translate into strategies to deepen trust in areas aligned with the three factors they positively correlated with trust: integrity, structural assurance, and identification. By mapping our preservation activities and choices onto the Yakel *et al.* model, we can better understand how the themes that emerged during our certification readiness assessment align with and inform our broader approach to cultivating trust among our stakeholders.

Integrity

The concept of integrity is, at its core, about setting and meeting expectations. Reliability builds credibility over time and signals our dedication to

providing a consistent service. When expectations are clearly defined and reliably met, it reduces uncertainty and reinforces trust—especially during times of transition or change. One area where we have invested significant effort is our Preservica documentation and training materials. Historically, we have made these available to our stakeholders in a variety of ways that were not uniformly presented. Starting in 2023, we undertook a comprehensive documentation review led by Digital Preservation Librarian Grete Graf. This included improving existing materials, developing new training modules, and restructuring and reorganizing our documentation into a more intuitive Sharepoint site. Improving the clarity, consistency, and accessibility of our resources will foster greater confidence in our services, support smoother onboarding and training, and ultimately strengthen the foundation we have already built with our stakeholders for transparent and reliable collaboration moving forward.

Another avenue we are pursuing to cultivate trust through integrity is by codifying and formalizing our incident response procedures. Initiated and led by our new Head of Digital Preservation David Cirella, the end goal of establishing a framework for service standards is to provide users with a more consistent set of expectations when disruptions occur. The structured incident response approach categorizes issues into five severity levels, from critical data loss (Level 1) to minor deficiencies (Level 5). Each level triggers a specific response protocol that includes ticket creation, targeted communication with relevant stakeholders, and engagement with appropriate support teams. The framework establishes clear escalation pathways and accountability measures, ensuring that incidents are addressed efficiently and transparently for affected users and system administrators.

Identification

Identification is the process of deeply understanding a designated community so that an organization can anticipate, interpret, and effectively respond to its evolving needs. This kind of comprehensive

awareness is essential for building trust, particularly in environments where user needs are complex and constantly evolving. When organizations can intuitively grasp what their communities value and require—often before those needs are explicitly stated—they are better positioned to design responsive services, make thoughtful decisions, and demonstrate long-term relevance.

A critical step in strengthening identification at Yale is refining our definition of our designated community of users. While the concept of designated community has been studied and critiqued within the OAIS reference model [20], we recognize the need to better define the user groups we serve. However, one of the complexities of Yale's digital preservation program is the diversity of our user base. We serve 19 distinct campus units, including the Law Library, University Archives, Yale's museums and galleries, and Yale Library's special collections repositories. Each of these units represents a community with individual needs, disciplinary norms, resourcing levels, and expectations for digital preservation. Not only this, but these units themselves serve their own user communities—researchers, students, faculty, and the public—whose needs and expectations cascade inward to ultimately shape the evolving preservation landscape at Yale. In this sense, our designated communities are nested like matryoshka dolls, with the digital preservation program situated several layers removed from many of the ultimate end-users. This means our designated community is not monolithic but rather a constellation of communities with overlapping but distinct requirements. This complexity presents both a challenge and an opportunity for building trust through identification. Understanding and translating each of our communities' needs into functional solutions that will work in their specific organizational context requires a commitment to deep and sustained stakeholder engagement.

To demonstrate that we truly understand each partner, we are soliciting direct feedback from

stakeholders through a series of meetings and listening sessions designed to help us understand their current and future needs. These semi-structured conversations, which began in Spring 2025, will provide a critical opportunity for our Head of Digital Preservation to determine whether we are meeting expectations and identify opportunities to improve our services so that they are more attuned to the unit-specific contexts in which they are used. These sessions are not only a chance to gather actionable feedback, but also to signal a culture of responsiveness and collaboration. Ultimately, these conversations will help us better understand the unique and varied needs of our designated communities so that we can better leverage identification to build a more user-focused, service-oriented approach.

Structural Assurance

Structural assurance is the visible guarantee of a repository's reliability. In other words, it is the sum of all interactions, experiences, and credentials through which trust is earned, sustained, and scaled. Offering stakeholders concrete evidence that the repository is competent and accountable substantiates a repository's preservation capabilities, allowing it to move beyond self-declarations of trustworthiness to demonstrable proof of preservation capabilities. This assurance can take many forms, including third-party certifications. Although we have not followed through with external certification yet, this may be a route we choose to pursue in the future. But structural assurance is not limited to formal assessments; it also manifests in how repositories design services, support users, perform outreach, and deliver consistent, meaningful results.

At Yale, one of our most impactful opportunities to demonstrate structural assurance lies in our commitment to meeting users where they are. Many of our stakeholders come from non-technical backgrounds, yet they are responsible for stewarding complex digital collections. To support them, we've collaborated with IT to build a robust technical infrastructure that includes tailor-made

tools, automated workflows, and system optimizations to make the ingest and access process appear seamless and turnkey.

Our unit support model, where a dedicated Digital Preservation Librarian liaises one-on-one with units to provide responsive repository support as well as providing scaled, sustainable future repository and integrated system planning serves as a useful mechanism to sustain trust. This support is built over years of collaboration, and can include iterative collection planning meetings to review content needs prior to system ingest, focused and individualized training, and ongoing on-demand troubleshooting support services. Personalized support and reduced barriers build user confidence while demonstrating the practical reliability at the heart of structural assurance.

Because so much of this back-end work happens out of view from our stakeholders, we recognize the importance of making that work visible. One area where we are eager to invest more time and effort is in outreach—specifically through storytelling. Sharing details about the work that happens behind the scenes, the ways we partner with other Yale units and external organizations, and the solutions we develop not only surfaces the broader impacts of our work, but also invites further engagement. This could be through strategic communications, data storytelling that can engage with our growing repository reporting infrastructure, or public-facing updates that give stakeholders a window into recent developments, milestones, and ongoing projects.

VII. AREAS FOR FUTURE WORK

Trust is a core concept within digital preservation, and user trust in repositories remains an emerging area of study in the digital preservation community. Although the digital preservation community has long engaged with different trust frameworks, there is a need to explore alternative measures of trust that go beyond existing tools. Currently, the primary mechanisms available to evaluate and measure trust in digital repositories can be costly, burdensome,

and difficult to implement consistently across institutions. Uptake remains low, and the results can be difficult to compare or apply meaningfully.

By mapping the positively correlated components of user trust identified by Yakel *et al.* onto current practices at Yale Library, we have begun to develop a more nuanced approach toward how to conceptualize and build trust with our users, which can strengthen future self-assessment or external certification approaches. While our work highlights the potential of user-centered approaches, it is important to acknowledge their limitations. For some organizations—particularly federal agencies, governmental bodies, or national libraries—formal certification frameworks may play a more vital role. In these contexts, certification provides an externally validated mechanism of accountability that can be critical for maintaining public trust, demonstrating compliance with policy or regulatory requirements, and ensuring transparency across large and complex constituencies.

Future research could therefore explore when certification is most effective and how user-centered practices might complement, rather than replace, these more formalized approaches. Alternatively, another possible avenue for future work could be the development of a more nuanced, flexible tool or framework for measuring or assessing trust that reflects the full range of how trust is built, demonstrated, and experienced.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Trust is foundational to the success and sustainability of digital preservation programs. Historically, attaining an external certification as a TDR has been considered the gold standard of demonstrating trustworthiness. Yale has considered—but ultimately never followed through with formal certification. Through our 2024 certification readiness assessment, we surfaced questions about how trust is established with stakeholders, and whether external certification is

the most effective—or only—mechanism for conveying trustworthiness. Drawing on the empirical model proposed by Yakel *et al.*, we explored how Yale's program enacts trust through three user-centered dimensions: integrity, identification, and structural assurance. These factors offered a valuable lens through which to analyze our existing practices and affirmed that trust is cultivated not only through compliance with standards, but also through transparency, responsiveness, and ongoing engagement and relationship-building with users.

By mapping the positively correlated components of user trust identified by Yakel *et al.* onto current practices at Yale Library, we identified ways in which our program communicates consistency and accountability (integrity), engages deeply with diverse stakeholder needs (identification), and demonstrates technical and organizational reliability (structural assurance). In doing so, we offer a more holistic consideration of trust that moves beyond, but does not discount, more formal assessment or certification. Our findings contribute to the broader digital preservation discourse by demonstrating how institutions can nurture trust through concrete, user-facing actions—even in the absence of certification. As the field continues to grapple with questions of accountability and sustainability, we argue that developing more flexible, nuanced approaches to assessing trust rooted in users' day-to-day engagement with repository services will be essential. This represents a gradual shift away from an early focus on technical standards and compliance towards a more holistic consideration of how repositories cultivate, sustain, and demonstrate trust to their communities. This evolution not only strengthens the field's internal practices but enriches our collective understanding of what it truly means to be a trusted digital repository.

Future work might further develop and test alternative tools and frameworks across diverse institutional contexts. This could include a deeper exploration of the instances in which formal certification may still be a critical component of trust-building, such as those for which accountability is

structured around statutory mandates or public oversight. In these cases, the rigor and external validation offered by certification can provide an assurance of trustworthiness that user-centered practices alone may not deliver.

In a field where credibility is essential and resources are finite, a more balanced future may lie in expanding our understanding of the interplay between formal certification and user-centered approaches, recognizing that distinct organizational contexts may call for different strategies, and that both can contribute meaningfully to building and sustaining long-term trust.

REFERENCES

- [1] ISO 16363:2025 (CCSDS 652.0-M-2). Space data information transfer systems - Audit and certification of trustworthy digital repositories. 2025.
- [2] E. Yakel, I.M. Faniel, and L.P. Robert Jr, "An empirical examination of data reuser trust in a digital repository," *Journal of the Assoc. of Info. Sci. and Technology*, vol. 75, iss. 8, pp. 898-915, Aug. 2024, doi: 10.1002/asi.24933.
- [3] "Home: Digital Preservation at Yale University Library" Accessed: Apr. 14, 2025. [Online.] Available: <https://guides.library.yale.edu/digitalpreservation/welcome>
- [4] "Yale University Report to the Digital Library Federation," Vol. 5, No. 1, Fall 2004. Accessed: Apr. 14, 2025. [Online.] Available: https://old.diglib.org/pubs/news05_01/yalenews5.pdf
- [5] M. Phillips, J. Bailey, A. Goethals, and T. Owens, "The NDSA Levels of Preservation: An explanation and uses", 2013. Accessed: Apr. 14, 2025. [Online.] Available: <https://osf.io/dpnqs>
- [6] Digital Preservation Coalition Rapid Assessment Model (version 3 - March 2024). Accessed: Apr. 14, 2025. [Online.] doi: [10.7207/dpcram24-03](https://doi.org/10.7207/dpcram24-03)
- [7] Digital Preservation Coalition. *Digital Preservation Handbook*, 2nd ed. (2015) Accessed: Apr. 14, 2025. [Online.] Available: <https://www.dpconline.org/handbook>
- [8] M. Lindlar and F. Schwab, "All that work...for what? Return on investment for Trustworthy

- Archive Certification processes - a case study," in: Proceedings of the 15th Int. Conference on Dig. Preservation, Sept. 24-28, 2018.
- [9] E. Maemura, N. Moles, and C. Becker, "Organizational assessment frameworks for digital preservation: A literature review and mapping," *Journal of the Assoc. of Info. Science and Technology*, vol. 68, iss. 7, pp. 1619-1637, July 2017. doi: [10.1002/asi.23807](https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23807).
- [10] M. Lindlar and P. Rudnik, "All eyes on Core Trust Seal - Reflections on repository type, designated community, and level of curation in RO," in: Proceedings of the 16th Int. Conf. on Dig. Preservation, September 16-20, 2019.
- [11] R. Frank, "Repository staff perspectives on the benefits of trustworthy digital repository certification," in: Proceedings of the 19th Int. Conf. on Dig. Preservation, Sept. 19-22, 2023.
- [12] D. Donaldson, I. Dillo, R. Downs, and S. Ramdeen, "The perceived value of acquiring Data Seals of Approval," *Int. Journal of Dig. Curation*, vol. 12, no. 1, 2017. [Online.] Available: <https://ijdc.net/index.php/ijdc/article/view/481>
- [13] CoreTrustSeal, Accessed: Apr. 14, 2025. [Online.] Available: <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>
- [14] Nestor Working Group Trust Repositories - Certification, "Nestor Criteria: Catalogue of criteria for Trusted Digital Repositories, Version 2," Accessed: Apr. 14, 2025. [Online.] Available: <https://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:0008-2010030806>
- [15] E. Yakel, I. Faniel, and A. Kriesberg, "Trust in Digital Repositories," *Int. Journal of Dig. Curation*, vol. 8, iss. 1, pp. 143-156, 2013. doi: 10.2218/ijdc.v8i1.251.
- [16] A. Yoon, "End users' trust in data repositories: definition and influences on trust development," *Arch. Sci.*, vol. 14, pp 17-34, 2014. doi: 10.1007/s10502-013-9207-8
- [17] G. Bak, "Trusted by whom? TDRs, standards culture and the nature of trust," *Arch. Sci.*, vol. 16, pp 373-402, 2016. doi: 10.1007/s10502-015-9257-1.
- [18] S. Abrams, "Tacit attitudinal principles for evaluating digital preservation success," *Arch. Sci.*, vol. 21, pp. 295-315, 2021. doi: 10.1007/s10502-021-09360-5.
- [19] T. Evans, "Are we winning? Other measurables for digital preservation," in: Proceedings of the 17th Int. Conf. on Dig. Preservation, Oct. 19-22, 2021.
- [20] R. Bettavia, "The power of imaginary users: Designated communities in the OAIS reference model," *Proceedings of the Assoc. for Info. Sci. and Technology*, vol. 53, iss. 1, pp. 1-9, 2016. doi: 10.1002/pr2.2016.14505301038.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Lauren Work is a Digital Preservation Librarian at Yale University Library.

Shira Peltzman is the Associate Director of Preservation Digital Strategies at Yale University Library.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Thank you to the Yale University Library Digital Preservation and Software Preservation and Emulation staff who participated in the certification readiness assessment and provided feedback on the ideas in this paper.

ChatGPT (4o) was used to correct grammatical errors or spelling mistakes and improve the readability of this paper.

